

Toward Non-Contact Chicken Egg Quality Monitoring With 77–81 GHz FMCW mmWave Radar: A Two-Arm Study with Destructive Validation and Longitudinal Tracking

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Abstract—This paper investigates the feasibility of using 77–81 GHz frequency-modulated continuous-wave (FMCW) millimeter-wave (mmWave) radar for non-contact chicken egg quality monitoring. The study is organized as two complementary arms. The first arm is a cross-sectional destructive-validation study in which different eggs of the same batch of 24 eggs were measured over 8 storage days and linked to mass, albumen and yolk indices, pH, candling observations, and breakout-derived quality scores. The second arm is a longitudinal nondestructive study in which the same three eggs were tracked for 8 days and linked to non-destructive ground truth data such as mass loss and candling-derived air-cell metrics. Raw radar data were acquired using a TI AWR1843EVM BOOST with a DCA1000EVM at a fixed 0.40 m antenna-to-egg distance from multiple side and vertical views. A target-locked processing pipeline, quality-control filtering, egg-level feature aggregation, and machine-learning regression were used to connect radar features to ground truth. The cross-sectional arm provided weak-to-moderate supporting evidence, whereas the longitudinal arm produced strong monotonic radar-to-ground-truth associations and strong leave-one-egg-out prediction results. The best longitudinal models achieved R^2 values of 0.899 for air-cell area, 0.918 for air-cell depth, 0.917 for mass-loss percentage, and 0.884 for a nondestructive core score. These results position high-frequency FMCW mmWave radar as a promising solution for egg quality monitoring in storage environments such as farms, food-processing facilities, and retail backrooms.

Index Terms—chicken egg quality monitoring, egg freshness, FMCW radar, millimeter-wave radar, non-destructive sensing, machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Egg freshness is important to food quality, process control, shelf-life management, and consumer confidence. Traditional egg assessment methods such as candling, breakout inspection, and internal-quality measurements remain useful, but many of the strongest freshness indicators are destructive, labor-intensive, or difficult to scale for continuous monitoring [1], [2]. Recent reviews further show that the modern egg-quality literature is dominated by optical, spectroscopic, and image-based nondestructive methods rather than by high-frequency radar sensing [3], [4].

A broad range of nondestructive modalities has already been explored for egg freshness assessment, including electronic nose sensing [5], ultrasound [6], dielectric spectroscopy [7], hyperspectral imaging [8], [9], infrared thermal imaging [10], real-time hyperspectral freshness inspection [11], and near-infrared spectroscopy [12]. These studies collectively demonstrate that egg freshness can be inferred from measurable physical changes during storage, but they also illustrate recurring practical tradeoffs involving lighting sensitivity, surface cleanliness, shell-color variability, destructive labeling burden, or the difficulty of integrating laboratory methods into continuous industrial monitoring workflows [3], [4].

Egg storage also produces predictable physical changes that are relevant to sensing. Prior work has reported storage-time-dependent weight loss, albumen thinning, yolk changes, and air-cell growth, with temperature and handling conditions strongly affecting deterioration rates [13], [14]. These observations motivate sensing modalities that can respond to internal moisture redistribution, dielectric change, and structural reorganization without breaking the shell.

Electromagnetic sensing is attractive in this context because water content, air-cell evolution, and internal layer redistribution can alter reflected or transmitted signals. Lower-frequency microwave imaging has already been explored for egg-related screening [15], and mmWave sensing has shown promise in other food and biological monitoring problems, including fruit property estimation [16], live-fish monitoring [17], fruit-quality imaging [18], and nondestructive testing more broadly [19]. However, based on the literature reviewed for this paper, we found little evidence of published work that directly studies 77–81 GHz FMCW mmWave radar for chicken egg quality monitoring while combining both destructive cross-sectional validation and same-egg longitudinal tracking. This gap motivates the present study.

The main contributions of this paper are threefold. First, we present a two-arm experimental design that combines a cross-sectional destructive-validation dataset with a longitudinal nondestructive dataset. Second, we develop a target-locked

FMCW mmWave radar processing and quality-control pipeline for multi-view egg measurements. Third, we evaluate machine-learning models that connect radar features to destructive and nondestructive egg-quality targets, showing that the longitudinal arm provides the strongest evidence chain for temporal freshness tracking.

II. RELATED WORK

The egg-freshness literature is mature in terms of problem importance but heterogeneous in sensing modality. Early reviews emphasized the need for nondestructive egg-quality measurement and summarized acoustic, spectroscopy-based, and other industrial inspection approaches [1], [2]. More recent reviews show a strong shift toward optical and spectroscopic systems, especially hyperspectral imaging, visible/near-infrared sensing, and machine-learning-assisted imaging pipelines [3], [4].

Representative examples include electronic-nose-based freshness prediction [5], ultrasound-based freshness estimation [6], dielectric spectroscopy combined with machine learning [7], and several hyperspectral and near-infrared methods [8]-[12]. These studies report strong performance under controlled conditions, but most remain tied to optical access, spectral instrumentation, or lower-frequency electromagnetic measurements. By contrast, radar-based food sensing has been studied more extensively for fruits, liquids, and broader food-security applications than for shell eggs [15]-[18].

This prior work motivates two observations. First, the general idea of nondestructive egg monitoring is well established. Second, there remains room for high-frequency radar methods that are non-contact, lighting-independent, compact, and potentially compatible with future automated storage-room or conveyor-side monitoring systems. The present work therefore does not claim to be the first nondestructive egg-quality study overall; rather, it targets an underexplored sensing regime and contributes an evidence-based feasibility study for 77-81 GHz FMCW mmWave radar.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Design

The study was organized as two complementary arms. The first arm was a cross-sectional destructive-validation study. Eggs purchased from a retail store were measured over 8 storage days, but different eggs were broken on different days for destructive ground truth. The second arm was a longitudinal nondestructive study in which three intact eggs were tracked repeatedly across the same 8-day interval. The two-arm design was chosen deliberately: the cross-sectional arm enabled linkage to strong internal-quality labels, whereas the longitudinal arm enabled within-egg tracking without repeatedly breaking the same sample.

Table I summarizes the final study design, retained analysis subsets, and validation schemes used in the paper. The cross-sectional arm contributed 17 egg-level rows to the main destructive-regression subset, while the longitudinal arm contributed 24 egg-day rows to the main nondestructive-regression

subset. The paper is intentionally written so that the longitudinal arm provides the main temporal-monitoring evidence and the cross-sectional arm provides supporting destructive-ground-truth evidence.

B. Radar Hardware and Acquisition Geometry

Raw radar data were acquired using a TI AWR1843EVM BOOST together with a DCA1000EVM capture card. The experiments used high-frequency FMCW mmWave sensing in the 77-81 GHz band. The nominal antenna-to-egg distance was fixed at 0.40 m for both study arms. For side-view measurements, each egg was laid horizontally on foam and captured from front, left, right, and back views. For vertical measurements, each egg was placed vertically on a thin plastic holder so that top and bottom views could be captured. Matched background captures were also acquired to support background subtraction and target locking.

1) *FMCW Data-Collection Physics and Parameter Calculations*: The data-collection configuration was selected so that each egg was measured as a compact dielectric target near the known 0.40 m range. The transmitted FMCW chirp can be represented by (1), where f_c is the carrier frequency, S is the chirp slope, and t is fast time. This chirp model and the beat-frequency range relationship are the basis of the range processing used in this paper [20], [21].

$$s_{\text{tx}}(t) = A_{\text{tx}} \exp \left[j2\pi \left(f_c t + \frac{S}{2} t^2 \right) \right]. \quad (1)$$

A reflector at range R produces a two-way delay $\tau = 2R/c$, and dechirping converts that delay into the beat frequency in (2). Therefore, range is estimated from the measured IF beat frequency using (3) [20].

$$\tau = \frac{2R}{c}, \quad f_b = S\tau = \frac{2SR}{c}. \quad (2)$$

$$R = \frac{cf_b}{2S}. \quad (3)$$

For the present measurements, $S = 60.012 \text{ MHz}/\mu\text{s} = 60.012 \times 10^{12} \text{ Hz/s}$ and the nominal egg distance was $R = 0.40 \text{ m}$. Substitution into (2) gives the expected egg beat frequency in (4).

$$f_b = \frac{2(60.012 \times 10^{12})(0.40)}{2.9979 \times 10^8} = 1.60 \times 10^5 \text{ Hz} \approx 160 \text{ kHz}. \quad (4)$$

The ADC captured $N = 512$ samples per chirp at $f_s = 12.5 \text{ Msps}$. Thus, the sampled fast-time aperture and effective sampled bandwidth are given by (5) and (6).

$$T_{\text{ADC}} = \frac{N}{f_s} = \frac{512}{12.5 \times 10^6} = 40.96 \mu\text{s}. \quad (5)$$

$$B_{\text{ADC}} = ST_{\text{ADC}} = (60.012 \times 10^{12})(40.96 \times 10^{-6}) \approx 2.46 \text{ GHz}. \quad (6)$$

TABLE I
TWO-ARM STUDY DESIGN. THE CROSS-SECTIONAL ARM PROVIDES DESTRUCTIVE-GROUND-TRUTH SUPPORT, WHILE THE LONGITUDINAL ARM PROVIDES WITHIN-EGG TRACKING EVIDENCE.

Study arm	Eggs	Days	Measurement design	Radar views	Ground truth	Main subset	analysis	Validation used	Main role in paper
Cross-sectional destructive arm	24 eggs	8 storage days	Different eggs measured each day	Front, left, right, back, top, bottom	Mass, yolk index, albumen index, pH, candling, breakout	17 egg-level rows		Leave-one-out CV	Supporting destructive-ground-truth evidence
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	3 eggs tracked repeatedly	8 storage days	Same eggs tracked over time	Front, left, right, back, top, bottom	Mass loss, candling-derived air-cell metrics, nondestructive score	24 egg-day rows		Leave-one-egg-out CV	Main temporal tracking and ML evidence
Common radar setup	-	-	TI AWR1843EVM BOOST + DCA1000EVM, FMCW mmWave	Egg side and vertical orientations	Nominal antenna-to-egg distance fixed at 0.40 m	Parser radar	ti_lane2; profile variant norm_pos	QC filtering before egg-level aggregation	Shared sensing backbone across both arms

The corresponding range-bin spacing follows (7). This calculation gives approximately 6.1 cm. Because a chicken egg has dimensions on the same order as this range spacing, the measured target response should be interpreted as a compact multilayer scattering signature rather than as a cleanly separated image of shell, air cell, albumen, and yolk layers.

$$\Delta R = \frac{c}{2B_{ADC}} = \frac{2.9979 \times 10^8}{2(2.46 \times 10^9)} \approx 0.061 \text{ m.} \quad (7)$$

Each capture contained 64 frames with a 100 ms frame periodicity and 128 chirps per frame. The capture duration and chirp count are therefore given by (8). This repeated-chirp design allows the range response to be averaged across many chirps and four receive channels, which is important because the egg return is weak, multilayered, and sensitive to small placement changes.

$$T_{\text{capture}} = 64 \times 100 \text{ ms} = 6.4 \text{ s,} \quad N_{\text{chirps}} = 64 \times 128 = 8192. \quad (8)$$

The measurement concept and radar geometry is shown in Fig. 1. A processing-flow summary is shown in Fig. 2. These two figures are important because they clarify both the physical acquisition setup and the radar-to-feature conversion used later in the learning pipeline.

C. Ground Truth and Retained Targets

The cross-sectional arm collected mass, yolk and albumen pH, candling observations, and breakout-derived structural measurements such as yolk and albumen indices. The longitudinal arm collected repeated nondestructive measurements, including mass, mass loss relative to Day 1, candling-derived air-cell area, air-cell depth, air-cell width, air-cell fraction, and a composite nondestructive core score. After screening the labels for relevance, redundancy, and reliability, a final target hierarchy was locked before modeling.

Table II lists the ground-truth targets retained for the main paper. In the cross-sectional arm, the primary regression targets were breakout core score, albumen index, and yolk index. In the longitudinal arm, the primary regression targets were mass loss from Day 1, air-cell area, and air-cell depth. Mass and several composite or secondary targets were retained only as supporting analyses rather than as the main headline results.

Fig. 1. Controlled experimental setup of radar data acquisition geometry.

1) *Electromagnetic, Chemical, and Biological Basis of 8-Day Monitoring*: The physical reason that mmWave radar can respond to egg quality is that the egg is a lossy multilayer dielectric object. The propagation path includes air, shell, membranes, albumen, yolk, and the air cell. Each layer can be described by a complex permittivity as shown in (9), where the real part stores electric-field energy and the imaginary part represents dielectric loss. Egg dielectric studies show that dielectric properties depend on composition, moisture content, temperature, and frequency; egg white has higher dielectric properties than yolk largely because egg white has much higher water content [22], [23].

TARGET-LOCKED FMCW mmWAVE RADAR PIPELINE

Fig. 2. Overview of the target-locked FMCW mmWave radar processing and learning pipeline. Multi-view egg radar captures were parsed, background-subtracted, target-locked, quality-controlled, and aggregated into egg-level radar features, which were then linked to destructive cross-sectional and nondestructive longitudinal ground truth for regression modeling and evaluation.

TABLE II
FINAL GROUND-TRUTH TARGETS RETAINED FOR MODELING.

Study arm	Paper label	Column name	Priority	Task type	Why retained
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Breakout core score (0–100)	breakout_core_score_0_100	Primary	Regression	Main destructive freshness target
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Albumen index	albumen_index	Primary	Regression	Main destructive structural target
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Yolk index	yolk_index	Primary	Regression	Main destructive structural target
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Mass (g)	mass_g	Secondary	Regression	Supporting physical target
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Mass loss from Day 1 (%)	mass_loss_pct_from_day1	Primary	Regression	Main temporal freshness target
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Air-cell area (px)	aircell_area_px	Primary	Regression	Main candling-derived target
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Air-cell depth (px)	aircell_depth_px	Primary	Regression	Main candling-derived target
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Air-cell width (px)	aircell_width_px	Secondary	Regression	Supporting candling-derived target
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Nondestructive core score (0–100)	nondestructive_core_score_0_100	Secondary	Regression	Composite nondestructive summary target
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Mass (g)	mass_g	Secondary	Regression	Supporting physical target

$$\epsilon^* = \epsilon' - j\epsilon''.$$
 (9)

At an interface between two dielectric regions, a simplified normal-incidence reflection coefficient is given by (10). Therefore, if storage changes the effective permittivity of albumen, yolk, membranes, or the air-cell boundary, the radar reflection coefficient also changes. This provides the electromagnetic link between egg-quality evolution and the measured residual radar profile.

$$\Gamma = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon_2^*} - \sqrt{\epsilon_1^*}}{\sqrt{\epsilon_2^*} + \sqrt{\epsilon_1^*}}.$$
 (10)

The biological aging process provides the source of these dielectric and geometric changes. During storage, water vapor and CO₂ leave the egg through the porous shell. The shell

and cuticle allow gas exchange while protecting the egg contents, and storage studies identify weight loss, air-cell growth, Haugh-unit decrease, albumen-height decrease, and pH increase as important storage-dependent quality changes [24], [25]. Water-vapor diffusion can be summarized by the Fick-type relation in (11), where J_w is water-vapor flux and dC_w/dx is the moisture concentration gradient across the shell and membranes.

$$J_w = -D_w \frac{dC_w}{dx}.$$
 (11)

The first-order mass-loss mechanism can also be expressed conceptually as (12), where A_{shell} is shell area, P_{shell} is an effective permeability, and the driving term is the water-vapor pressure difference between the egg interior and the surrounding environment.

$$\frac{dm}{dt} \propto -A_{\text{shell}} P_{\text{shell}} (p_{w,\text{inside}} - p_{w,\text{outside}}). \quad (12)$$

CO₂ loss also changes internal chemistry. Dissolved CO₂ participates in the carbonate buffer reactions in (13). As CO₂ escapes through the shell, the equilibrium shifts, hydrogen-ion concentration decreases, and albumen pH increases according to (14). Storage studies report rapid albumen pH increase, air-cell enlargement, weight loss, and quality deterioration with increasing storage time and temperature [24], [25].

$$\text{pH} = -\log_{10} [\text{H}^+]. \quad (14)$$

The growth of the air cell can be linked to moisture loss by the approximate volume relation in (15), where Δm_w is water mass lost and ρ_w is water density. This relation is not a complete gas-transport model, but it explains why mass loss and air-cell metrics can evolve together during storage.

$$\Delta V_{\text{air}} \approx \frac{\Delta m_w}{\rho_w}. \quad (15)$$

These chemical and biological changes influence the radar in three coupled ways. First, moisture redistribution changes the effective permittivity. Second, air-cell growth increases contrast between a low-permittivity gas region and water-rich albumen. Third, albumen thinning and yolk/albumen redistribution shift the locations of internal scattering boundaries. Thus, storage does not simply reduce radar amplitude; it changes the egg's multilayer dielectric scattering state.

D. Radar Signal Processing and Feature Extraction

A target-locked radar processing pipeline was applied to both study arms. The raw captures were parsed using the `ti_lane2` mode selected by parser comparison. Range-domain profiles were extracted and converted to a normalized positive residual representation after matched background subtraction. Target locking was performed around the nominal 0.40 m distance using a constrained search window and local quality-control logic. Captures were then filtered using peak-location, target-window-energy, and ambiguity criteria before egg-level aggregation.

Only a conservative subset of radar features was retained for modeling. The trusted main predictors were side-view and vertical-view peak amplitude, target-window energy, ROI energy, target-to-ROI energy ratio, and peak range, together with compact side-versus-vertical contrast features. Features judged fragile or over-dependent on local processing artifacts were excluded from the main models. This conservative feature policy was important because the dataset is small and feasibility-oriented.

1) *Detailed Range-Profile Processing and Feature Definitions:* The raw DCA1000 binary stream was parsed into complex ADC samples $x[n, m, q]$, where n is chirp index, m is receive-channel index, and q is fast-time sample index. The selected parser was `ti_lane2`, consistent with the parser-selection step in the processing code. Before range transformation, a per-chirp mean was removed as shown in (16) to suppress DC offsets and near-zero-frequency leakage.

$$\tilde{x}[n, m, q] = x[n, m, q] - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{q=0}^{N-1} x[n, m, q]. \quad (16)$$

A Hanning window $w[q]$ was then applied and a range FFT was computed along the fast-time dimension. The range spectrum for each chirp and receive channel is written in (17). The range-axis mapping in (18) is the discrete version of the FMCW relationship in (3).

$$X[n, m, k] = \sum_{q=0}^{N-1} \tilde{x}[n, m, q] w[q] \exp\left(-j \frac{2\pi k q}{N}\right). \quad (17)$$

$$R_k = \frac{c}{2S} \left(\frac{k f_s}{N} \right). \quad (18)$$

A stable capture-level range profile was obtained by non-coherently averaging FFT magnitudes across all chirps and receive channels as shown in (19). This averaging treats the egg as a static target during each 6.4 s capture while improving repeatability.

$$P_{\text{egg}}(R_k) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{chirps}} N_{\text{RX}}} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{chirps}}} \sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{RX}}} |X[n, m, k]|. \quad (19)$$

Because the radar also receives reflections from the foam, plastic holder, tripod, table, and static room clutter, matched background captures were used. The measured profile can be decomposed conceptually as (20), and the egg-related residual profile is computed using (21).

$$P_{\text{meas}}(R) = P_{\text{egg}}(R) + P_{\text{background}}(R) + P_{\text{multipath}}(R) + n(R). \quad (20)$$

$$P_{\text{res}}(R_k) = P_{\text{target}}(R_k) - P_{\text{bg}}(R_k). \quad (21)$$

The main profile used in the analysis was a normalized positive residual, shown in (22). This representation suppresses static background structure and emphasizes positive target-related changes relative to the matched background.

$$P_{\text{norm,pos}}(R_k) = \max \left\{ \frac{P_{\text{target}}(R_k) - P_{\text{bg}}(R_k)}{P_{\text{bg}}(R_k) + \epsilon}, 0 \right\}. \quad (22)$$

Target locking was performed because the egg was expected near 0.40 m. The algorithm searched within $W_T = [0.30, 0.50]$ m and selected the local target peak by (23). This prevents

unrelated clutter peaks outside the expected egg distance from being selected as egg features.

$$R_{\text{peak}} = \arg \max_{R \in W_T} P_{\text{norm,pos}}(R), \quad W_T = [0.30, 0.50] \text{ m}. \quad (23)$$

The retained feature set was intentionally conservative. Peak amplitude, target-window energy, ROI energy, target-to-ROI energy ratio, centroid, and spread can be defined using (24)-(29). These features describe not only the strength of the radar return but also its location, concentration, and range-domain distribution.

$$A_{\text{peak}} = \max_{R \in W_T} P_{\text{norm,pos}}(R). \quad (24)$$

$$E_T = \int_{R_1}^{R_2} P_{\text{norm,pos}}(R) dR. \quad (25)$$

$$E_{\text{ROI}} = \int_{R_{\text{min}}}^{R_{\text{max}}} P_{\text{norm,pos}}(R) dR. \quad (26)$$

$$\eta = \frac{E_T}{E_{\text{ROI}} + \epsilon}. \quad (27)$$

$$\bar{R} = \frac{\int R P_{\text{norm,pos}}(R) dR}{\int P_{\text{norm,pos}}(R) dR + \epsilon}. \quad (28)$$

$$\sigma_R = \sqrt{\frac{\int (R - \bar{R})^2 P_{\text{norm,pos}}(R) dR}{\int P_{\text{norm,pos}}(R) dR + \epsilon}}. \quad (29)$$

E. Modeling Protocol

The machine-learning workflow was also locked before running the final experiments. For the cross-sectional arm, leave-one-out cross-validation was used because each row corresponded to a different egg in the final destructive subset. For the longitudinal arm, leave-one-egg-out cross-validation was used to prevent leakage of egg-specific signatures between training and test folds. Within each outer training fold only, preprocessing consisted of median imputation, variance filtering, high-correlation filtering, standardization, and top-k Spearman feature selection.

Regression was treated as the main task type throughout the paper. The model set was intentionally conservative and appropriate for small-sample analysis, including Elastic Net, support vector regression with radial basis function kernel, ExtraTrees, and an adaptive partial least squares variant. Performance was reported using mean absolute error (MAE), root-mean-square error (RMSE), coefficient of determination (R^2), Pearson correlation, and Spearman correlation. For the longitudinal arm, mean within-egg correlations were also reported.

IV. RESULTS

A. Capture-Level Quality Control and Radar Signature Behavior

Table III summarizes the capture-level quality-control outcomes. In the cross-sectional arm, side views achieved a 96.9% QC pass rate, vertical views achieved 68.8%, and all views together achieved 87.5%. In the longitudinal arm, side views achieved a 92.7% pass rate, vertical views achieved 75.0%, and all views together achieved 86.8%. Across both study arms, side views were more stable than vertical views, which is consistent with the later feature-selection and modeling results.

Table 3 summarizes the capture-level QC results after target-locking and ambiguity filtering.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 summarize the cross-sectional and longitudinal radar behavior, respectively. In the cross-sectional arm, QC-passed mean profiles and heatmaps showed usable but limited day separation. In the longitudinal arm, the same-egg measurements displayed much clearer temporal organization, especially in the side-view signatures. This difference is important: it suggests that within-egg temporal change is easier to observe than between-egg change when biological variability is not controlled. Figure 5 summarizes the longitudinal non-destructive ground-truth evolution across the 8-day storage period. The measured trends are physically consistent with expected egg-quality degradation during storage. In particular, mass loss from Day 1 increased progressively, while candling-derived air-cell metrics such as air-cell area and air-cell depth also increased over time. At the same time, the nondestructive core score decreased with storage day, reflecting the overall deterioration trend. These trajectories are important because they confirm that the longitudinal arm captured meaningful within-egg freshness changes rather than random measurement fluctuations. When interpreted together with the clearer temporal organization observed in the radar signatures in Fig. 4, Fig. 5 provides the ground-truth basis for the strong longitudinal radar-to-target associations and machine-learning results reported later in Table IV, Fig. 7, Table VI, and Fig. 9.

It is important that Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 are not interpreted as requiring a simple monotonic decrease in peak magnitude or target-window energy. The mmWave response is a coherent sum of shell, membrane, albumen, yolk, air-cell, holder, and residual-background components. A compact expression is given in (30), where each internal boundary contributes with its own amplitude, reflection coefficient, range, and phase.

$$X(R_k) \approx \sum_{i=1}^M a_i \Gamma_i \exp\left(-j \frac{4\pi R_i}{\lambda}\right) W(R_k - R_i) + n_k. \quad (30)$$

At 77 GHz, the wavelength is given by (31). A 1 mm change in effective path length produces the two-way phase change in (32), which is nearly 185 degrees. Therefore, small internal shifts caused by air-cell growth, albumen thinning, yolk/albumen redistribution, or small placement differences can change constructive interference into destructive interfer-

TABLE III
CAPTURE-LEVEL QUALITY-CONTROL OUTCOMES AFTER TARGET LOCKING AND AMBIGUITY FILTERING.

Study arm	View group	Target captures	QC-passed captures	QC pass rate (%)
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Side	96	93	96.9
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Vertical	48	33	68.8
Cross-sectional destructive arm	All views	144	126	87.5
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Side	96	89	92.7
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Vertical	48	36	75.0
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	All views	144	125	86.8

ence. This explains why peak magnitude and target-window energy can fluctuate even when biological aging is progressive.

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f_c} = \frac{2.9979 \times 10^8}{77 \times 10^9} \approx 3.89 \text{ mm.} \quad (31)$$

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{4\pi\Delta R}{\lambda} = \frac{4\pi(1 \text{ mm})}{3.89 \text{ mm}} \approx 3.23 \text{ rad.} \quad (32)$$

For this reason, the paper frames the radar evidence through target-locked, background-subtracted, multiview, aggregated features and regression against ground truth rather than through a single visually decreasing amplitude curve. This interpretation is also consistent with the stronger longitudinal results, where the same eggs were tracked repeatedly and biological between-egg variability was reduced.

B. Radar-to-Ground-Truth Associations

Table IV reports the strongest retained radar-to-ground-truth association for each target. The cross-sectional destructive arm produced only weak or at best modest associations in the final high-confidence subset. The strongest cross-sectional entry was vertical target-window energy versus mass, with Spearman rho = 0.438, while the other main cross-sectional targets remained weak. These findings indicate that the destructive arm is useful for support and interpretation, but not as the main source of strong predictive evidence in this paper.

By contrast, the longitudinal nondestructive arm produced strong monotonic relationships. Side-view ROI energy was the strongest radar feature for all retained longitudinal targets, with Spearman rho values of 0.966 for air-cell area, 0.966 for air-cell depth, 0.970 for air-cell width, 0.958 for mass-loss percentage, and -0.970 for the nondestructive core score. The corresponding Benjamini-Hochberg q-values were all highly significant, ranging from 5.89e-14 to 2.50e-12. These results provide the clearest evidence that the radar signatures were tracking physical egg changes over time rather than only random day-to-day variation.

The scatter-plot summaries in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 visually reinforce this difference between study arms. Fig. 6 should be interpreted conservatively because the cross-sectional associations are modest and sample-limited. Fig. 7 is more compelling: the strongest pooled longitudinal associations are nearly monotonic and align with expected storage behavior such as increasing air-cell size and increasing mass loss.

C. Machine-Learning Performance

Table V summarizes the best cross-sectional models under leave-one-out validation. The strongest cross-sectional result was albumen index using the side-only feature block with ExtraTrees, which achieved MAE = 0.004, RMSE = 0.006, $R^2 = 0.291$, Pearson r = 0.540, and Spearman rho = 0.472. The other cross-sectional targets were notably weaker. Breakout core score achieved $R^2 = -0.011$ even with fused features, mass achieved $R^2 = 0.097$, and yolk index remained below zero. Accordingly, the destructive arm should be interpreted as supporting evidence rather than as a strong stand-alone predictive dataset.

Table VI presents the main machine-learning results of the paper. Under leave-one-egg-out validation, the longitudinal fused feature block with ExtraTrees achieved $R^2 = 0.899$ for air-cell area, 0.918 for air-cell depth, 0.917 for mass-loss percentage, and 0.884 for the nondestructive core score. Spearman correlations for these targets ranged from 0.963 to 0.970. Air-cell width was also predicted strongly, with Adaptive PLS reaching $R^2 = 0.872$. Mass itself was harder to predict in an absolute sense, but even there the within-egg correlations remained positive. These results show that the radar data are much more effective for relative temporal tracking than for absolute destructive-label prediction across different eggs. The main reason behind these contrasting results of longitudinal and cross sectional study is the biological variability of eggs in a batch of eggs.

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 display the predicted-versus-true plots for the best models from the two study arms. The cross-sectional plots in Fig. 8 show larger dispersion and weaker alignment to the identity line. In contrast, the longitudinal plots in Fig. 9 show markedly tighter agreement for the principal nondestructive targets. This visual comparison supports the central paper narrative that longitudinal same-egg tracking is the main strength of the proposed radar framework.

D. Feature-Block Ablation

Table VII compares side-only and fused feature blocks. In the cross-sectional arm, side-only features were generally as good as or better than fusion except for a small gain on breakout core score. In the longitudinal arm, fusion improved R^2 slightly for every retained target, but the gains were modest: Delta R^2 was 0.008 for mass loss, 0.007 for air-cell area, 0.010 for air-cell depth, 0.006 for air-cell width, and 0.004 for the nondestructive core score. This means that

Fig. 3. Cross-sectional radar signature evolution and feature structure. QC-passed daily mean profiles, day-wise heatmaps, side-view and vertical-view feature trends, and PCA projection for the cross-sectional arm. The figure shows that the side-view signatures contain more stable structure than the vertical-view signatures, but day separation remains limited.

Fig. 4. Longitudinal radar signature evolution and temporal separation. QC-passed daily mean profiles, day-wise heatmaps, side-view and vertical-view feature trends, and PCA projection for the longitudinal arm. Compared with the cross-sectional arm, the same-egg longitudinal data show clearer temporal organization and stronger day-related structure.

side views dominate the predictive story, while vertical views provide a limited but measurable complementary contribution.

Table 7 compares side-only versus fused feature blocks. This table supports the ablation discussion.

V. DISCUSSION

The results support the feasibility of 77-81 GHz FMCW mmWave radar for non-contact egg quality monitoring, but the evidence is not uniform across tasks. The strongest evidence

Figure 5. Longitudinal non-destructive ground-truth trajectories.

Fig. 5. Longitudinal non-destructive ground-truth trends across the 8-day storage period. The figure shows progressive mass loss, air-cell growth, and deterioration in the composite nondestructive quality score for the same eggs tracked over time.

TABLE IV

STRONGEST RADAR-TO-GROUND-TRUTH ASSOCIATION FOR EACH RETAINED TARGET. CROSS-SECTIONAL CORRELATIONS ARE WEAK AND SHOULD BE FRAMED AS SUPPORTING ONLY; LONGITUDINAL CORRELATIONS ARE THE MAIN EVIDENCE CHAIN.

Study arm	Target	Best radar feature	n	Spearman ρ	Pearson r	BH q -value	Signal strength
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Albumen index	Vertical peak range	15	0.287	0.156	0.960	Weak
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Breakout core score (0–100)	Vertical peak range	15	0.185	0.159	0.970	Weak
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Mass (g)	Vertical target-window energy	15	0.438	0.176	0.770	Moderate
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Yolk index	Vertical peak range	15	0.287	0.194	0.902	Weak
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Air-cell area (px)	Side ROI energy	24	0.966	0.944	2.61E-13	Strong
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Air-cell depth (px)	Side ROI energy	24	0.966	0.957	2.61E-13	Strong
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Air-cell width (px)	Side ROI energy	24	0.970	0.957	5.89E-14	Strong
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Mass (g)	Side ROI energy	24	-0.714	-0.601	0.00116	Strong
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Mass loss from Day 1 (%)	Side ROI energy	24	0.958	0.944	2.50E-12	Strong
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Nondestructive core score (0–100)	Side ROI energy	24	-0.970	-0.946	5.89E-14	Strong

TABLE V

BEST CROSS-SECTIONAL MODELS UNDER LEAVE-ONE-OUT VALIDATION ON THE LOCKED 17-ROW SUBSET.

Target	Feature block	Model	n	MAE	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	Spearman ρ
Albumen index	Side only	ExtraTrees	17	0.004	0.006	0.291	0.540	0.472
Breakout core score (0–100)	Side + vertical fused	ExtraTrees	17	24.17	30.053	-0.011	0.234	0.150
Mass (g)	Side only	SVR (RBF)	17	2.424	3.165	0.097	0.354	0.201
Yolk index	Side only	SVR (RBF)	17	0.023	0.027	-0.113	-0.354	-0.412

Fig. 6. Cross-sectional top radar-to-ground-truth scatter plots. The strongest cross-sectional radar associations are modest and are therefore treated as supporting evidence rather than headline proof.

comes from the longitudinal arm, where the same eggs were tracked over time and strong monotonic relationships emerged between radar features and nondestructive ground truth. In practical terms, this suggests that high-frequency FMCW radar may be especially useful for temporal monitoring scenarios in which each egg or tray is observed repeatedly during storage, rather than for one-shot prediction of destructive quality labels across a highly variable population.

1) *Interpretation of Non-Monotonic Radar-Amplitude Features:* The absence of a clear decreasing trend in peak magnitude and target-window energy should not be treated as a failure of the sensing mechanism. Aged eggs undergo moisture loss, CO₂ loss, pH increase, albumen thinning, air-cell growth, and internal liquid redistribution, but the radar amplitude is not a direct biochemical freshness variable. Instead, it is the magnitude of the coherent multilayer scattering response in

Longitudinal top pooled radar-target correlations

Fig. 7. Longitudinal top radar-to-ground-truth scatter plots. The strongest pooled longitudinal radar features, especially side-view ROI energy, show strong monotonic relationships with mass loss, air-cell growth, and the nondestructive quality score.

(30). Depending on the relative phase and dielectric contrast of the shell, air-cell, albumen, and yolk contributions, storage can increase energy in one range bin while decreasing it in another.

The strongest claim supported by the present data is therefore not that one radar amplitude feature decreases monotonically with storage day. The stronger and more defensible claim is that storage changes the egg's effective dielectric

and geometric scattering state, and that this state can be represented by multiview target-locked radar features. This framing explains why the cross-sectional arm, which compares different eggs across days, is weaker, while the longitudinal arm, which tracks the same eggs repeatedly, produces the most coherent radar-to-ground-truth relationship.

The side-view dominance observed throughout the study is also physically plausible. Side views likely captured a

TABLE VI

BEST LONGITUDINAL MODELS UNDER LEAVE-ONE-EGG-OUT VALIDATION. THESE ARE THE HEADLINE MACHINE-LEARNING RESULTS FOR THE PAPER.

Target	Feature block	Model	n	MAE	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	Spearman ρ	Mean within-egg ρ	Mean within-egg r
Air-cell area (px)	Side + vertical fused	ExtraTrees	24	838.541	1179.070	0.899	0.950	0.963	0.984	0.968
Air-cell depth (px)	Side + vertical fused	ExtraTrees	24	4.092	5.402	0.918	0.960	0.963	0.984	0.974
Air-cell width (px)	Side + vertical fused	Adaptive PLS	24	7.536	11.024	0.872	0.936	0.947	0.968	0.967
Mass (g)	Side only	Elastic Net	24	1.185	1.376	-0.324	0.096	0.219	0.778	0.810
Mass loss from Day 1 (%)	Side + vertical fused	ExtraTrees	24	0.141	0.221	0.917	0.960	0.970	0.984	0.975
Nondestructive core score (0–100)	Side + vertical fused	ExtraTrees	24	3.267	4.785	0.884	0.942	0.963	0.984	0.965

Fig. 8. Cross-sectional best-model predictions. Predicted-versus-true plots for the best cross-sectional models under leave-one-out validation. These results are weaker than the longitudinal results and should be discussed conservatively.

TABLE VII

SIDE-ONLY VERSUS FUSED FEATURE-BLOCK ABLATION.

Study arm	Target	Best side-only model	Side-only R^2	Best fused model	Fused R^2	ΔR^2	Preferred block
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Breakout core score (0–100)	ExtraTrees	-0.075	ExtraTrees	-0.011	0.064	Fused
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Albumen index	ExtraTrees	0.291	ExtraTrees	0.065	-0.226	Side
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Yolk index	SVR (RBF)	-0.113	SVR (RBF)	-0.113	0.000	Side
Cross-sectional destructive arm	Mass (g)	SVR (RBF)	0.097	ExtraTrees	-0.003	-0.099	Side
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Mass loss from Day 1 (%)	ExtraTrees	0.910	ExtraTrees	0.917	0.008	Fused
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Air-cell area (px)	ExtraTrees	0.893	ExtraTrees	0.899	0.007	Fused
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Air-cell depth (px)	ExtraTrees	0.908	ExtraTrees	0.918	0.010	Fused
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Air-cell width (px)	Elastic Net	0.887	ExtraTrees	0.893	0.006	Fused
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Nondestructive core score (0–100)	ExtraTrees	0.880	ExtraTrees	0.884	0.004	Fused
Longitudinal nondestructive arm	Mass (g)	Adaptive PLS	-0.312	Elastic Net	-0.293	0.020	Fused

more stable combination of shell curvature, internal liquid distribution, and air-cell-related contrast than the top and

bottom views. Vertical measurements were still useful, but their quality-control rates were lower in both study arms. The

Fig. 9. Longitudinal best-model predictions. Predicted-versus-true plots for the best longitudinal models under leave-one-egg-out validation. These are the main ML results supporting the feasibility claim.

ablation results therefore suggest a practical system design strategy: side-view radar should be the baseline sensing mode, whereas vertical views can be added when modest complementary gains justify the extra acquisition complexity.

The paper should also be interpreted in light of its limitations. The cross-sectional destructive subset is small, and its weaker predictive results indicate that it is not sufficient by itself to support aggressive claims about generalized destructive-label prediction. The longitudinal arm includes only three eggs, which is enough for a feasibility study but not enough for broad population generalization. The experiments were performed under controlled geometry with a fixed radar-to-egg distance and carefully matched backgrounds; future work should test robustness to carton variability, denser packing, larger sample counts, different shell colors, temperature regimes, and more realistic storage-room or conveyor conditions. In addition, the present work focused on egg-level radar features rather than fully learned end-to-end representations from raw radar cubes, because leakage-safe small-data modeling was a more defensible first step.

Even with these limitations, the two-arm design strengthens the paper substantially. The destructive arm anchors the study to established egg-quality metrics, while the longitudinal arm demonstrates that the same eggs evolve coherently in radar

space and ground-truth space. This combination is more convincing than either arm alone. It supports the claim that high-frequency FMCW mmWave radar can contribute meaningfully to future storage-room egg monitoring systems, especially when the goal is relative change detection, trend tracking, and non-contact freshness screening rather than exact laboratory replacement.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a two-arm feasibility study on chicken egg quality monitoring using 77-81 GHz FMCW mmWave radar. A longitudinal nondestructive arm and a cross-sectional destructive-validation arm were designed to answer complementary questions. The cross-sectional arm provided weak-to-moderate supporting evidence, whereas the longitudinal arm produced strong radar-to-ground-truth associations and strong leave-one-egg-out regression performance for mass-loss percentage, air-cell size, and a composite nondestructive quality score. The results show that high-frequency FMCW mmWave radar is a promising non-contact sensing modality for egg quality monitoring and justify larger future studies targeting denser sampling, broader environmental variation, and more deployment-oriented storage scenarios.

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